

INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF ADVANCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES: EFFECTS OF TREATMENT OF CARBON FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

The surface free energy and composition of carbon fiber showed strong correlation with its treatment history. In this report, the untreated AU, the surface-oxidation-treated AS, and the heat-treated (under vacuum) AHT carbon fibers were used in Poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK) and Poly(ether sulphone) (PES) composite systems. The relationships between treatment of carbon fibers (thus surface characteristics of carbon fibers) and the interfacial properties of advanced thermoplastic composites were investigated. Both single-fiber-composite samples and

prepreg-made composite laminates were studied. The effects of carbon fiber surface compositions were also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites have excellent mechanical properties and design flexibility. The necessity to reduce weight in high performance applications has led a rapid rise in the use of structural composite materials. However, the efficiency of utilizing the strength and stiffness of reinforcement fibers is essentially dependent upon the degree of adhesion between fiber and matrix. Oxidative surface treatments may improve the adhesion level. The improved adhesion is generally caused by the chemical interaction between carbon fiber surface oxides and the reactive groups of the matrix materials [1]. The effects of oxidative surface treatment and further heat treatment under vacuum of carbon fibers had been analyzed and quantified [2]. The surface free energy and surface composition of carbon fibers both showed strong correlation with the treatment history. The oxidation treatment increased the surface free energy of carbon fiber by introducing functional group elements (oxygen and nitrogen). On the other hand, further heat treatment under vacuum reduced the surface free energy by removing those added elements away from the surface of carbon fiber. In this report, the untreated AU, the surface-oxidation-treated AS, and the heat-treated AHT carbon fibers were used in Poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK) and Poly(ether sulphone) (PES) composite systems. The relationships between treatment of carbon fibers (thus surface characteristics of carbon fibers) and the interfacial properties of advanced thermoplastic composites were investigated. Both single-fiber-composite samples and unidirectional composite laminates have been studied. The effects of carbon fiber surface compositions (quantified by x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy) on the fiber/matrix adhesion level were also discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two methods have been commonly used to study the shear strength of an interface in composites: (1) the fiber pull-out method and (2) the single-fiber-composite method [3-5]. The fiber pull-out technique is useful with glass fibers, but is much more difficult to use with the brittle and small carbon fibers. The single-fiber-composite technique is a straightforward experimental procedure. One 1-cm-long carbon fiber can be embedded in a tensile dogbone coupon of matrix polymer. The coupon is subjected to a tensile loading. The tensile stresses are then transferred to the fiber through the shear stresses at the fiber-matrix interface. The geometries of the single-fiber-composite specimens are sketched in Fig. 1. The corresponding

stress distributions along the fibers during testing are shown in Fig. 2. Since the maximum strain of the brittle carbon fiber is much lower than that of the polymer, the fiber fractures into small fragments within the matrix. This fracture process continues until the interfacial stresses no longer induce fracture of carbon fiber. The maximum fiber length that survives is known as the critical fiber length L_c . Based on the force balance in a micromechanical model, Kelly and Tyson [6,7] proposed that

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2L_c} \quad (1)$$

where τ is the interfacial shear strength, σ_f is the fiber failure stress at the critical fiber length L_c , and d is the diameter of the fiber. L_c/d is also called the critical aspect ratio. The actual fragment length varies between $L_c/2$ and L_c , with a mean of $3/4L_c$ [8]. Eqn (1) assumes a uniform strength along the fiber. However, this is generally not true for the strong and brittle carbon fibers because of the flaws in the material.

Figure 1. Single-fiber-composite specimen geometry.

Figure 2. The corresponding stress distribution along the fiber during testing ($\sigma_1 < \sigma_2 < \sigma_3$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

L_c in PES Matrix

Untreated AU, surface-treated AS and heat-treated AHT carbon fibers were used to make single-fiber-composite specimens. One 1-cm-long carbon fiber was centered inside each 100 mm x 25 mm x 0.16 mm PES matrix sample by compression molding. 3600P PES powders were sieved before use. The particle size was controlled to be less than 500 μm to avoid air bubbles. The fiber/PES assembly was then heated at 380°C without applying significant pressure for 3 min. After the PES was 'molten' in the press, the molding pressure was gradually increased up to 3 MPa for a brief pause of 20 seconds. The whole assembly was then immediately transferred to a pneumatically controlled cold press. The cold press removed the heat and allowed the 1-cm-long carbon fiber to be embedded in a solidified PES matrix. The specimens were then cut into the specimen size specified in Fig. 1, using a steel rule die.

The dogbone tensile coupons were pulled by a mechanical tester at a crosshead speed of 1.3 mm/min at room temperature until failure. To observe the fiber fragments within the matrix, the specimen had to be either heat-remelted or solvent-dissolved to allow the fiber fragments to be separated by flow. Consequently, each tested specimen was dissolved by cyclopentanone. In order to prepare the sample for examination under the microscope, the dissolving process was performed on a glass slide. Gentle heating was used. After the solvent was evaporated, a thin layer of PES was deposited on the glass slide and became ready for examination.

The averaged critical fiber length L_c and critical aspect ratio L_c/d of each group of carbon fibers in PES matrix were listed in Table 1. Each data entry was the result of three to six specimens tested. Ten to fifteen fiber fragments were collected per specimen. There was a 16% decrease in the critical aspect ratio from AU to AS fibers. This indicated a 16% increase in the interfacial shear strength while the fiber failure stresses had been assumed to be more or less identical within the same matrix system. This also suggested a dominant role of fiber surface energetics on the interfacial shear strength in PES composites. The results of AHT fibers were generally similar to those of AU fibers, except that AHT300 (heat-treated up to 300°C) showed behavior similar to those of AS fibers. It was noted that the standard deviations in Table 1 were as high as 20–40% of the measured L_c . However, this testing technique should give fiber fragment lengths of $(3/4 \pm 1/4)L_c$ [8], which was $(3/4L_c) \pm 33\%$. Therefore, the high standard deviations were expected and the testing results were used for comparison purpose only.

Table 1. Critical length of carbon fiber in PES matrix.

Sample	AS	AHT300	AHT700	AHT1000	AU
L_c (mm)	0.439 (0.113)	0.433 (0.223)	0.531 (0.313)	0.532 (0.170)	0.512 (0.128)
L_c/d	63	62	76	76	73
Surface Free Energy (dyne/cm)	49.8	46.0	31.7	33.0	31.5

(Standard deviations are shown in parentheses)

L_c in PEEK Matrix

Single-fiber-composite specimens were also prepared from 150P PEEK. Fine, sieved powders of PEEK were used. The particle size was less than 250 μm . The molding procedure was similar to the one used for PES samples, except that PEEK was melted at 400°C. Due to the fast cooling rate during the solidification in the pneumatically controlled cold press, PEEK became amorphous and was transparent.

PEEK single-fiber-composites were pulled under tension using the same testing conditions for PES specimens. However, the PEEK matrix was so tough that it almost never broke through during testing. The test was then stopped when the elongation of the specimen had exceeded 20% of its original length. To observe the fiber fragments within the PEEK matrix, the tested specimens were dissolved on a glass slide using sulfuric acid. The acid was carefully dropped onto the PEEK sample. Gentle heating was necessary at this stage to ensure dissolution of the PEEK matrix. The glass slides were then examined under a microscope. The results of averaged critical fiber length and critical aspect ratio of each group of carbon fibers in PEEK matrix have been shown in Table 2. Fifty to one hundred fiber fragments were counted for each group. The critical aspect ratio of AS carbon fibers in PEEK matrix was almost only one half of that of AU carbon fibers. This suggested a 100% improvement in the interfacial shear strength between PEEK matrix and carbon fibers. On the other hand, like the results in the PES matrix, the results of AHT fibers in the PEEK matrix were very close to those of AU fibers. The heat treatment of carbon fibers seemed to have removed the active surface oxides, thus greatly reduced the interaction between carbon fiber surface and PEEK matrix.

Table 2. Critical length of carbon fiber in PEEK matrix.

Sample	AS	AHT300	AHT500	AHT1000	AU
L_c (mm)	0.250 (0.150)	0.471 (0.199)	0.470 (0.276)	0.480 (0.240)	0.484 (0.227)
L_c/d	36	67	67	69	69
Surface Free Energy (dyne/cm)	49.8	46.0	45.4	33.0	31.5

(Standard deviations are shown in parentheses)

PES Composite Laminates

Some PES composite prepregs of 68% by weight of fiber have also been prepared from these carbon fibers, using solution impregnation technique [9]. The prepregs were then dried and layed up for compression molding according to the following procedure. All samples were held at 350°C for 15 min under zero pressure to eliminate residual solvent and then pressed for 5 min at 3 MPa before cooling under pressure. The initial cooling rate was about 10°C/min. Unidirectional composite panels of 12 plies were prepared for transverse flexural tests. The short-beam shear strength (SBSS) was measured on 24-ply unidirectional samples. The interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IC}) was determined using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens. Table 3 summarized the results of transverse flexural modulus (TFM), transverse flexural strength (TFS), SBSS and G_{IC} of the PES composite laminates. Each data represented the average of the results of five or more specimens, except that only two DCB specimens were prepared for each G_{IC} data. Here, PES composites made from AS carbon fibers showed distinct mechanical properties when compared with the samples made from AU carbon fibers. TFS increased 20%, SBSS improved 26%, and G_{IC} was up 61%. The effects of surface treatment of carbon fibers on the interfacial properties of PES composites were then quantified. However, the results of TFM were essentially the same because of the domination of the moduli of reinforcing carbon fibers. TFM was therefore not a sensitive means in describing the fiber-matrix adhesion level in composites.

The effects of heat treatment of carbon fibers on the interfacial properties of PES composites were more difficult to be defined. The heat treatment under vacuum removed varying amount of oxygen and nitrogen elements from carbon fiber surface. This process simultaneously reduced the surface free energy of carbon fibers. In the single-fiber-composite study, results showed a

Table 3. The mechanical properties of PES composite laminates.

Carbon Fiber	TFM (GPa)	TFS (MPa)	SBSS (MPa)	G (KJ/m ²)
AS	8 (0.5)	48 (4)	72 (1)	1.08 (0.1)
AHT300	8 (0.5)	45 (5)	-	-
AHT500	9 (0.5)	63 (5)	-	-
AHT700	7 (0.5)	55 (5)	-	-
AHT1000	7 (0.5)	40 (5)	-	-
AU	7 (0.2)	40 (3)	57 (2)	0.67 (0.1)

(Standard deviations are shown in parentheses)

decrease in the interfacial shear strength of carbon fibers in both PEEK and PES matrices because of the heat treatment. However, there seemed to be a maximum in the results of TFS around the heat treatment temperature of 500°C in Table 3. Interestingly, x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS or ESCA) results of Na concentration also showed a similar trend [2]. Alkaline salt additives had been reported to result in postpolymerization or crosslinking of aromatic polymers [10], such as PEEK and PES. The variation in surface sodium concentration due to the heat treatment process might have then affected the molecular weight distribution of PES matrix near carbon fiber surfaces. This would be an interesting area for future study. On the other hand, the molecule segregation might be faster in the solution system [11]. Since these PES composites were prepared by a solution impregnation technique, the effects of surface sodium salts on PES molecules near fiber surfaces could be even more complicated. These would all influence the performance of such composite systems.

CONCLUSIONS

Optimum fiber-matrix adhesion was necessary for good translation of the fiber properties and full utilization of the matrix toughness in carbon-fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites. The oxidative surface treatments increased the surface free energy of carbon fiber by introducing functional group elements and could improve the adhesion between fiber and thermoplastic matrices. The interfacial shear strength was doubled in PEEK matrix and increased 16% in PES matrix, as revealed by single-fiber-composite testing. In addition, the study of PES composite laminates showed improvements of 20%, 26% and 61% in TFS, SBSS and G_{IC}, respectively,

when changed from AU to AS fiber systems. On the other hand, the heat treatment process reduced the surface free energy of carbon fiber by removing those functional group elements. The adhesion level between fiber and thermoplastic matrices was thus reduced. In the single-fiber-composite study, the interfacial shear strength of AHT fiber system has been decreased to the level of that of AU fiber system. However, the transverse flexural strength of PES composite showed an interesting variation with the surface sodium concentration of carbon fiber. The surface sodium may have induced the postpolymerization or crosslinking of PES matrix and influenced the performance of such composite material systems.

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